

ROLE OF MATHEMATICS AND IT IN TRAINING MODERN MANAGERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18217642>

In the process of building a new Uzbekistan, the development of the national economy on an innovative basis is emerging as a priority. In this process, the issues of raising the quality of education to world standards, training competitive personnel in the international labor market, and improving their professional competence are of urgent importance. In particular, in the process of training future management leaders in the higher education system, measures are being systematically implemented to create modern pedagogical conditions, bring them to a qualitatively new level, deepen professional qualifications, introduce new approaches, and effectively use innovative methods. In particular, the tasks set are: "Each higher education institution should establish direct cooperation with leading scientific and educational institutions of the world, strive for the widespread introduction of advanced technologies into the educational process, actively involve them in educational and methodological activities based on international educational standards, conduct master classes, organize advanced training courses for highly qualified teachers and scientists of friendly foreign educational institutions, systematically organize internships for young teachers and researchers on their basis, as well as retrain and improve the skills of professors and teachers." In implementing these tasks, it is advisable to qualitatively implement effective pedagogical conditions for training modern management personnel in the higher education system and further organize research aimed at increasing the effectiveness of targeted pedagogical, pedagogical-economic and pedagogical-psychological measures for training such personnel.

An analysis of foreign literature on the integration of AI, Data Science and Project Management in the development of professional competencies of managers trained in higher education institutions around the world shows different approaches to digitalization of education. The well-known economist Bond [7], having studied the experience of universities in the USA, Great Britain and Singapore, emphasizes the integration of artificial intelligence and data science into MBA programs.

Another researcher, Hetmańczyk [8], studying the digital deficit, found that there is a significant gap between basic and specialized skills among

students: 45% have basic skills, but only 18% know advanced analytical tools. This indicates the need to increase the share of Data Science. Another scientist, Farias-Gaytan [9], reveals that digital education is lagging behind in developing countries due to limited financing and digital resources. His conclusion shows that the process of digitalization of education is uneven in the world.

Including, S.S. Gulomov, M.T. Mirsolieva, M. Paradaev, Y.U. Ismadiyarov, O.Kh. Khamidov, M. Sharifkhodzhaev's works cover in detail the issues of improving the continuous professional training of managers and specialists. Also, theoretical and practical research in this area was conducted by N.Sh. Abdullayeva [1], N. Akhmedova [2], M. Innazarov [3], T. Kalmuratov [4], Sh. Nizamova, B. Ilhomov, J. Shaturaev.

The issues of quality monitoring in the education system and increasing its effectiveness have also been the focus of attention of a number of scientists. In particular, S.T. Turgunov [5], U.I. Inoyatov, U.Sh. Begimkulov [6] and others have developed theoretical foundations in this area and given practical recommendations. The specific aspects of management in higher education institutions and the issues of training managerial personnel in educational organizations are covered in depth in the studies of A. Egorshin and S. Reznik.

The effective formation of general scientific competence in future managers in the process of mathematical training is one of the important issues in the higher education system. The medium and long-term socio-economic development programs of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasize the need to update the concept of economic education, general approaches and the entire education system based on modern requirements. This will create an opportunity to train competitive and highly qualified managerial personnel who have not only a set of academic knowledge, but also the ability to solve complex tasks based on a creative approach.

In the system of higher economic education, mathematical knowledge is considered a fundamental basis, through which students develop general scientific competence, which is a necessary condition for successful professional activity in the future. Therefore, mathematical training should not be limited to information intended only for economic education, but should be enriched with new sections and topics, as well as introduce practice-oriented courses such as "Social and Economic Forecasting", "Mathematical Methods in Economic Research", "Additional Sections of Mathematics".

It is advisable to organize mathematical training on a modular basis, which should include such blocks as the fundamental "core", additional sections,

mathematical methods in economic research and socio-economic forecasting. Such an approach allows for the development of cognitive models of managers, the formation of experience in the practical application of mathematical knowledge, and the perfect development of motivational and reflexive competencies.

The observation method allows changes in the level of competence formation to be observed, the meaning of events in the educational process to be assessed. Tests are considered the most objective method, are based on standards and norms, and allow for comparison and comparison of results. Surveys analyze the level of formation of the cognitive-operational component in students. The results of scientific and educational research work provide information on the formation of the motivational-value component. Diagnostics, in turn, allows you to assess the results of education, predict and, if necessary, correct the process.

An analysis of school textbooks and curricula in our country has shown that graduates of secondary schools should have sufficient knowledge of computer science and achieve a basic level of digital literacy. At the same time, every year the number of school graduates choosing the national test block in computer science is increasing. However, since computer science is not specified as a compulsory subject in the entrance exams for pedagogical specialties, most applicants study this subject at school at the basic level.

Systematic and effective work on organizing activities aimed at forming digital skills allows you to bring the educational process closer to life and increase students' motivation to use digital technologies.

It was substantiated that the formation of general competence is a continuous process, which must be developed gradually throughout the entire period of education. The introduction of an integrated monitoring system in this process creates the opportunity for an objective and systematic assessment of the level of knowledge, skills and competence of students.

In conclusion, mathematics and information technology disciplines serve as a fundamental basis for the formation of professional competencies of future managers. Their deep integration into the educational process, their content and methodological modernization are important conditions for the training of highly qualified managerial personnel who are competitive, capable of strategic thinking and solving modern economic problems on a scientific basis.

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